

NAVIGATION SYSTEM BASED ON DIJKSTRA'S ALGORITHM WITH SPATIAL CONTEXT INTEGRATION

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Abstract

This paper introduces a pathfinding system tailored for blind and visually impaired users to navigate university campuses more effectively. The system utilizes a modified Dijkstra's algorithm combined with a coordinate-based framework and enriched environmental descriptions, considerably enhancing the effectiveness of navigational aids. By employing graph-based data structures, the layout of the campus is precisely modeled, with nodes depicting various locations (study rooms, lecture halls etc.) and edges providing detailed transit directions. This structured design allows the system to offer more accurate and user-friendly guidance, significantly improving navigation in complex indoor settings. Ultimately, this solution aims to increase the autonomy and safety of visually impaired individuals, making their campus navigation experience more seamless and intuitive.

Keywords: Algorithm Optimization · Software Architecture · Real-Time Systems · Computational Models · Accessibility Technology.

1. Introduction

Navigational challenges are substantial barriers for the visually impaired, particularly in complex environments like university campuses [1]. Existing solutions often lack context-specific instructions necessary for effective orientation [2]. This research introduces a navigation application tailored to the needs of the visually impaired finding their way, using a comprehensive graph-based representation of spatial layouts with fine-grained descriptions. Current technologies primarily focus on GPS-based outdoor navigation, overlooking the unique challenges introduced by indoor environments [3]. The need for precise and context-aware pathfinding within buildings remains largely unaddressed. This research aims to fill this gap by introducing a system that not only guides but also educates users about their surroundings using environmental cues.

The developed algorithm constructs a path from room A to room B with detailed text descriptions. The system interfaces with users through a screen reader [4], providing voice directions of the text descriptions that guide them through the campus efficiently. Until

now, the solution has been tested exclusively in a university campus setting; however, it is suitable for any complex case where the accuracy of indoor navigation is of primary importance. This method addresses the accessibility requirements necessary for blind and visually impaired individuals [5], ensuring they can navigate independently and safely.

2. System Architecture

2.1. Graph Construction

The system models the university campus as a directed graph where nodes represent specific locations (e.g., rooms, corridors, stairs) and edges denote possible paths between these locations, each tagged with weights (distance) and descriptive text (Fig. 1). This model allows for dynamic pathfinding and supports detailed, context-aware instructions necessary for blind and visually impaired users. Even though the number of edges at corners and cross-sections may seem redundant, this abundance is actually desired in case with the visually impaired to ensure that each edge describes the particular section as vividly as possible, so that the final text covers the entire path in great detail.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of the graph structure

Using the Python library NetworkX [6], the graph is constructed programmatically (Fig. 2). Each node and edge are inputted with specific attributes such as

coordinates and connectivity type (e.g., room to corridor, corridor to stairs), which are crucial for the subsequent pathfinding operations.

Procedure create_graph	
	Initialize a directed graph G
	Add a node labeled "F4.25" with coordinates (8, 2) and type "room" to G
	Add an edge from "F4.25" to "F4.25_c" with a weight of 2 and description "Walk three steps forward down the corridor"
EndProcedure	

Figure 2: Programmatic graph population

2.2 Pathfinding Algorithm

The core of the navigation system is a modified Dijkstra's algorithm, a method proven effective in various similar real-world applications [7] that computes the shortest path between any two nodes in the entire

graph (Fig. 3). This algorithm is enhanced by a method of angle calculation to determine the necessary turns at each step of the path based on the vector angles between consecutive edges.

Procedure find_shortest_path(graph, start_node, end_node)	
	Apply Dijkstra's algorithm to find the shortest path from start_node to end_node in graph
	Return the path
EndProcedure	

Figure 3: Dijkstra's algorithm

3. Navigation Guidance Logic

3.1. Reducing Redundancy

The system uniquely addresses the redundancy typically found in continuous corridor instructions. By

aggregating distances and simplifying instructions, the system reduces repetitive and confusing instructions (Fig. 4) - a crucial feature for visually impaired users.

If current_node is a corridor and next_node is a corridor then	
	Increment accumulated_distance by the weight of the edge
	Increment accumulated_nodes by 1
	Append a description "Walk straight ahead [accumulated_distance] steps in the corridor. Orient yourself to the rooms on your right: you will walk past [accumulated_nodes] rooms."
EndIf	

Figure 4: Reducing redundant descriptions

3.2. Turn Calculation and Directions

A key enhancement over basic Dijkstra's pathfinding is the implementation of turn directions derived from the calculated angles between path segments. Determining the turn direction changes poses a significant challenge: if the user has to turn left or right, how does the algorithm decide this, especially for nodes with several outgoing edges?

In the solution, each node is assigned specific coordinates, which together form a coherent coordinate system [8] within a floor. The algorithm analyzes the

current, previous and next nodes and calculates the angle between the two edges connecting these nodes. Based on this angle, the correct change of direction can be determined and added to the descriptions. If no rotation is necessary, the algorithm continues (Fig. 5). This method is universally applicable because the angle is always calculated with respect to an absolute axis. This feature directly impacts user experience by providing clear turn directions in any possible positioning of nodes in relation to each other.

Procedure calculate_turn_direction(angle1, angle2)	
	Compute angle_diff as (angle2 - angle1 + 180) modulo 360 - 180
	If angle_diff equals 90 then
	Return 'turn left'
	ElseIf angle_diff equals -90 then
	Return 'turn right'
	EndIf
EndProcedure	

Figure 5: Coordinate-based context

3.3. Detailed Algorithm Execution

To provide a clear illustration of how the enhanced algorithm operates in real-time, below are the logs captured during a typical navigation task on the university campus. They demonstrate the step-by-step computation and decisions made by the algorithm as it directs a

user from one location to another. Detailed node coordinates, weight of the edges, and the calculated angles are necessary for determining turn directions. Each entry shows how the system compiles comprehensive navigation instructions from individual segments of the path. For example, the algorithm decides to append a

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